

Briefing #3

Top 3 project achievements

1. The aggregation of the technical specifications in January into deliverable D1.2 “FAIRCORE4EOSC Technical Specifications” marked an important achievement for the project because the technical specifications are needed to kick-start the the development of the nine new EOSC Core components that the project will deliver to improve the discoverability of research outputs.
2. The internal technical and financial review showed that the project is on track despite few delays due to practical reasons. No major deviations were reported.
3. The FAIRCORE4EOSC Data Management Plan (DMP) was published on the DMP tool Argos at <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/dd4c79ed-1b43-41ad-81fa-f79da5af72eb> This version of the DMP is made before the bulk of the work of the project is carried out. The project DMP is a living document which will evolve as the work progresses, using the DMP versioning provided by Argos.

Technical updates

[Templates have been developed](#) for recording and analysis of compliance assessment regimes across a number of use cases identified in the Landscape Report, and analysis is in progress.

and expectations from the core components within their communities, specifically at the IS-ENES3 General Assembly Functional requirements for the FC4E components have been formalized and published on the project wiki following the provided guidelines.

Case Study Progress

Functional requirements for the FC4E components have been formalized and published on the project wiki following the provided guidelines. The climate change, European Integration of National-level Services and Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities case studies have been further discussing the requirements

The climate change, European Integration of National-level Services and Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities case studies have been further discussing the requirements and expectations from the core components within their communities, specifically at the IS-ENES3 General Assembly meeting, 16-18 January and the euroCRIS working group kick-off, 1st February. The

formalized requirements have been included in the D1.2 FAIRCORE4EOSC Technical Specifications deliverable, section 9 WP7 – User Requirements from the Case Studies. This emphasized the need to properly link the case study requirements to the requirements and work done in the specific components. This task will be taken up in the coming reporting period and is included as a session for the Technical All Hands Meeting, 18-20 April in Finland.

In addition to the requirements work, data management plans have been provided by the SSH, Mathematics, European Integration of National-level Services and Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities case studies. The climate case study is planning to provide a data management plan. These are first versions and are expected to be updated over time.

Next Steps

A technical project meeting in April in Finland will gather the Technical Steering Group members, development teams, Work Package Leaders and Task Members together to hear the External Advisory Board's feedback on the technical specifications and plan ahead the work towards BETA release in November 2023.

In March, FAIRCORE4EOSC will participate in Endorse - the European Data Conference on Reference Data and Semantics (14-16 March) as well as Research Data Alliance Plenary (21-23 March) where the project presents in Brokering Framework session on Thursday 23 March 11.00-12.30 CET and in the co-located Research Software Workshop organised with FAIR-IMPACT on Friday 24 March 9.00-12.00 CET.